

THE ROLE OF "BERAKHLAK" WORK CULTURE IN IMPROVING EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE WITH THE ADAPTABILITY AFTER POSITION EQUALIZATION AS A MEDIATION VARIABLE IN BONTANG CITY GOVERNMENT

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Abstract

Purpose: This study aims to analyze the role of BerAKHLAK work culture in accordance with the MENPAN-RB letter number 20 year 2021 on the employee performance with the adaptability after the equalization position from structural to functional as a mediation variable within the Bontang City Government. **Method:** It is a quantitative research using a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire survey approach. A sample of 82 employees ASN who experienced equalization of positions was selected according to purposive sampling criteria. Data analysis using Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS) with outer model, inner model, and bootstrapping testing. **Result:** The work culture did not have a big impact directly on performance (p-value 0.853), but it did have a big impact and significant effect on adaptability (p-value 0.001). Adaptability has a positive and significant effect on performance (p-value 0.000) and acts as a full mediator of the relationship between work culture and performance (p-value 0.000) with a contribution to explaining 81.3% of the variance in performance. **Practical Implications for Economic Growth and Human Capital Development:** Strengthening employee adaptation capacity with a training, coaching, mentoring, and a 360 degree feedback system is a key strategy for improving performance. This has an impact on the efficiency of public services, the optimization of professional human resources, the attractiveness of investment, and the growth of the MSME sector and creative industries in Bontang City as a partner area of the Ibu Kota Nusantara, the new capital city of Indonesia. **Novelty:** This study reveals the BerAKHLAK work culture does not have a direct impact on performance in the context of the Bontang City Government, because a strong local work culture has been embedded first (such as the slogan "extraordinary, professional, dignified"), so that adaptability is the only mechanism for channeling cultural influence on performance in the context of bureaucratic reform of equalization of positions.

Keywords: *BerAKHLAK Work Culture, Employee Performance, Adaptability, Equalization Position, Bureaucratic Reform, State Civil Apparatus*

INTRODUCTION

Bureaucratic reform in Indonesia has progressed with the release of PANRB Ministerial Regulation Number 17 of 2021, which addresses the equalization of administrative positions into functional positions. This policy mandates to all central and regional government agencies to simplify the organizational structure by transferring the structural positions (echelons III and IV) to functional positions. The main goal is to simplify the bureaucracy to create professional, competency-based services. The application of this policy also cuts the chain of hierarchy that has been slowing down decision-making and public services (Dessler, 2020; Robbins & Judge, 2024). In the Bontang City Government itself, this policy was implemented at the end of year 2021 by transforming 191 supervisory positions (echelon IV) into functional positions of second experts and 2 administrative positions (echelon III) into functional positions of intermediate experts. These structural changes have significant consequences for work patterns, career systems, and new competency demands that require employees' readiness to adapt. The phenomenon that occurs after the equalization of this position is that there is a gap between policy expectations and the reality of implementation. The results of initial observations of ten employees who experienced equalization indicated that

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many state civil servants (ASN) still had difficulty adapting to new roles and responsibilities. The transition from a commanding and hierarchical structural position to a functional position that requires autonomy, initiative, and performance achievements based on credit scores does not necessarily go smoothly. Dessler (2020) and Mondy & Martocchio (2016) emphasized that major organizational changes like this often face resistance, decreased motivation, and employee unpreparedness if they are not accompanied by appropriate change management strategies, including competency development and strengthening an adaptive work culture. Prior research has investigated the correlation among work culture, adaptability, and performance. Aggarwal (2024), Hung et al. (2022), and Pham et al. (2024) found that work culture has a significant effect on employee performance and behavior. Research by Brahm et al. (2024), Park et al. (2020), and Wallin (2024) proves that a positive work culture encourages employees' adaptability in the face of change. Meanwhile, Juna et al. (2024), Meng et al. (2024), and Fernandez et al. (2023) confirmed that individuals with high adaptability tend to perform better. The study by Srimulyani et al. (2025), Katsaros (2025), and Kim et al. (2025) even showed that adaptability plays a role as a mediator between organizational culture and performance. However, most of the research focused on the private sector and manufacturing, and more examined the direct influence between variables without exploring simultaneous mediation mechanisms in the context of public sector bureaucratic reform in Indonesia.

The originality of this research resides in its examination the role of adaptability mediation in the relationship between the work culture of BerAKHLAK launched by the Ministry of PANRB through Circular Letter Number 20 of 2021 and the performance of employees after equalization of positions within the local government. This research fills the research gap identified by Hasan (2023) about the limited empirical studies that examine the complex patterns of indirect influence of work culture on performance through mediation variables in the context of Indonesian bureaucracy. More detail, this study reveals that the unique findings of the BerAKHLAK work culture do not have a direct effect on performance because a strong local work culture has been embedded in the Bontang City Government, such as the slogan "ASN who is extraordinary, professional, dignified" which has been internalized through the Mayor's circular letter since 2016. So, adaptability is the only mechanism by channeling cultural influence on performance, a finding that differs from previous studies that generally found significant direct influences. Based on this background, this study aims to analyze the influence of work culture on the performance of Bontang City Government employees, analyze the effect of work culture on employee adaptability, analyze the effect of adaptability on employee performance, and analyze the role of adaptability the mediation of work culture on employee performance following the implementation of the equalization policy. The results of this study are expected to make a theoretical contribution to the development of public sector human resource management science, as well as practical implications for the formulation of policies to strengthen the adaptive capacity of civil servants in facing the dynamics of bureaucratic reform in Indonesia.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Hypotheses Development

Work culture on performance

The Organizational Culture Theory put forward by Robbins & Judge (2024, 561) affirms that work culture functions as a system of shared meaning that shapes the attitudes and behaviors of organizational members. A positive work culture is characterized by the values of collaboration, openness, integrity, and innovation that will create an environment that supports employee motivation, trust, and commitment. In this view, work culture acts as an informal control mechanism that directs employees to behave in accordance with organizational expectations, thereby directly encouraging increased productivity and effectiveness in task execution. Dessler (2020, 460) reinforces this argument by explaining that human resource management practices reflected in work culture such as reward systems, training, and development will shape positive work competencies and behaviors that impact individual and organizational performance. Thus, the stronger the implementation of a constructive work culture, the higher the tendency of employees to achieve optimal work results according to the set standards. Empirical research by Septa (2024) and Widodo (2025) confirms that a strong and supportive organizational culture plays a key driver in building employee engagement which has direct implications for productivity and the achievement of organizational targets.

H1: Work culture has a positive effect on performance

Work culture on adaptability

Organizational culture theory in the perspective of flexibility and innovation (Robbins & Judge, 2024, 565) explains that a culture that emphasizes openness to change, continuous learning, and risk-taking will encourage employees to more easily accept new ideas, adapt behaviors, and learn different ways of working when organizations

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face environmental dynamics. An adaptive work culture creates a safe psychological environment for employees to try new approaches and learn from mistakes without a fear. Within the framework of strategic Human Resource Management, Dessler (2020) emphasizes that HR practices such as training, development, and performance management that are aligned with the values of work culture will shape and strengthen employees' adaptive capacities. Mondy & Martocchio (2016, 36) view adaptability as a function of the flexibility of human resources, where a work culture that supports collaboration and learning facilitates the adjustment of employees' behaviors, skills, and attitudes to changes in policies, systems, and work demands. Lopes' research (2025) proves that organizational values that emphasize innovation, open communication, and cross-departmental collaboration make it easier for employees to accept change and be more confident in facing the transformation process. Sadikin *et al.* (2025) also affirm that an organizational culture that supports employee flexibility and participation significantly increases the level of adaptability of individuals and teams.

H2: Work culture has a positive effect on adaptability

Adaptability on performance

Human resource management theory and organizational behavior in the context of the VUCA environment (volatility, uncertainty, complexity, ambiguity) places adaptability as a critical predictor for performance. Robbins & Judge (2024, 72) explicitly state that in the modern world of work, adaptability is a core competency, where individuals with high agility can more effectively respond to change, learn new skills, and overcome ambiguity, which ultimately contributes to improved task performance and contextual performance. The Resource-Based View (RBV) theory put forward by Barney (2018) and Cameron & Quinn (2020) supports this argument by stating that adaptive ability is a valuable, scarce, and hard-to-replicate internal resource, which can be a source of an organization's competitive advantage. Individuals with high adaptive capacity are able to quickly transform their knowledge and skills to respond to the demands of a changing environment, creating added value for the organization. Research by Park *et al.* (2020) on workers in South Korea shows that career adaptability not only has a direct impact on in-role performance, but also strengthens extra-role performance through increased work attachment. Chen *et al.* (2021) in their literature study concluded that there are strong and significant positive effects of various adaptability constructs on performance measures, both subjective and objective.

H3: Adaptability has a positive effect on performance

Mediation of adaptability to work culture and performance

Robbins & Judge (2024, 355) explain that innovative culture breeds adaptive behavior and superior performance, and places adaptation as a key competency that connects HR practices and culture with employee performance outcomes. In this framework, work culture functions as an exogenous variable that creates conditions conducive to adaptive capacity development, then becomes an active mechanism that converts the cultural support into concrete actions that have an impact on the achievement of performance targets. The Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 1997) in Srimulyani *et al.* (2025) provides a more detailed explanation of this mediation mechanism. According to this theory, individuals learn and develop behavior through dynamic interactions between personal factors (cognitive, affective), environmental (organizational culture), and behavior itself. A work culture that supports learning and innovation forms employees' self-confidence in the face challenges of change, which then encourages adaptive behavior. It is this adaptive behavior that directly results in improved performance. Sari's research (2025) proves that a flexible work culture that supports learning first increases adaptive work behavior, and this increase in adaptive performance then contributes to the increase in individual and organizational performance. Srimulyani *et al.* (2025) and Katsaros (2025) also confirm the mediating role of adaptability in the relationship between organizational culture and performance. Thus, the influence of work culture on performance is not only direct, but also indirect through improving employee adaptability.

H4: Adaptability mediates the influence of work culture on performance

The conceptual framework in this study is built on theories related to human resource management, organizational behavior, as well as the results of previous research on the relationship between work culture, adaptability, and employee performance. This framework is designed to systematically describe the interconnections among the variables to be examined, both direct and indirect influences, so as to provide a clear direction for the implementation of research and hypothesis proofing. The conceptual model developed places work culture as an independent variable (exogenous), employee performance as a dependent variable (endogenous), and adaptability as a mediating variable (intervening) that connects the variables.

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Figure 1. Conceptual framework

Source: Previous research (2026)

METHOD

It is a quantitative research using a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire survey approach. A sample of 82 employees ASN who experienced equalization of positions was selected according to purposive sampling criteria. Data analysis using Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS) with outer model, inner model, and bootstrapping testing. This research location in Bontang City Government, East Kalimantan Province, Indonesia.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This study analyzes the influence of AKHLAK work culture on the performance of employees with the ability to adapt after equalization of positions as a mediation variable in the Bontang City Government. Data were obtained from 82 ASN respondents who met the inclusion criteria: ASN status, more than 5 years of service, and experienced equalization of positions from structural to functional. Descriptive analysis showed that respondents were dominated by men (54%), aged 46-55 years (50%), educated in D-IV/S1 (74.4%), and had a working period of more than 20 years (50%). All respondents (100%) are civil servants who experienced equalization at the end of 2021. The results of descriptive statistical analysis showed that the work culture variable had an average response of 4.51 (scale 1-5) with the collaborative indicator obtaining the highest score (4.60) and the adaptive indicator obtaining the lowest score (4.37). The adaptability variable had an average of 4.04 with the highest positive response indicators to training feedback (4.43) and the ability to learn new skills the lowest (3.83). The performance variable has an average of 4.16 with the highest quantity and punctuality indicators (4.21) and the lowest quality (4.06). Testing the measurement model (outer model) showed that all indicators had an outer loading value > 0.7 , thus meeting the convergent validity. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values for work culture (0.622), adaptability (0.708), and performance (0.768) > 0.5 , and Composite Reliability (CR) of each variable > 0.7 , indicate good reliability. The discriminant validity test with the Fornell-Larcker criterion showed that the square root of the AVE of each variable was higher than its correlation with the other variables, so that the model had sufficient discriminant validity.

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Table 1. Outer model check result

Variable	Indicator	Outer loading	CA	CR	Remark
Work culture (WC)	WC1	0,745	0,899	0,92	Valid
	WC2	0,732			Valid
	WC3	0,817			Valid
	WC4	0,847			Valid
	WC5	0,837			Valid
	WC6	0,755			Valid
	WC7	0,777			Valid
Adaptability (A)	A1	0,878	0,94	0,951	Valid
	A2	0,915			Valid
	A3	0,857			Valid
	A4	0,763			Valid
	A5	0,863			Valid
	A6	0,897			Valid
	A7	0,755			Valid
	A8	0,800			Valid
Performance (P)	P1	0,928	0,897	0,929	Valid
	P2	0,930			Valid
	P3	0,879			Valid
	P4	0,757			Valid

Source: Data processed (2026)

The structural model (inner model) test produced the following findings. The first, the direct influence of work culture on performance showed a negative path coefficient of -0.014 with a t-statistic of 0.185 (p-value 0.853), which was below the significance limit of 1.96. Thus, the first hypothesis (H1) that states that work culture has a positive effect on performance is rejected. The effect size (f^2) on this pathway was very small (0.001), indicating that work culture is not a significant predictor of performance directly. Second, the influence of work culture on adaptability showed a positive path coefficient of 0.447 with a t-statistic of 3.264 (p-value 0.001), which exceeded the significance limit. An effect size (f^2) of 0.250 is included in the category of large effects. Thus, the second hypothesis (H2) which states that work culture has a positive effect on adaptability is accepted.

Third, the effect of adaptability on performance showed a positive path coefficient of 0.908 with a t-statistic of 12.680 (p-value 0.000), far exceeding the significance limit. The effect size (f^2) of 3.533 falls into the category of very large effects. Thus, the third hypothesis (H3) which states that adaptability has a positive effect on performance is accepted. Fourth, mediation effect testing showed that the indirect influence of work culture on performance through adaptability had a path coefficient of 0.406 with a t-statistic of 3.730 (p-value 0.000), which was significant at a confidence level of 95%. Meanwhile, the direct influence of work culture on performance was not significant, indicating that adaptability plays a role as a full mediator in the relationship. Thus, the fourth hypothesis (H4) which states that adaptability mediates the influence of work culture on performance is accepted. The R-square value for the adaptability variable is 0.200, indicating that 20% of the adaptability variance is explained by work culture, while the rest is explained by other factors outside the model. The R-square value for the performance variable is 0.813, indicating that 81.3% of the performance variance is explained by work culture and adaptability together, which falls into the strong category. The fit model test showed an SRMR value of 0.075 (< 0.10), so the model was declared fit and worthy of further analysis.

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Table 2. Structural model check result

Source: Data processed (2026)

Path	Hyp	Coeff	T-stat	P-value	Result
Work culture → Performance	H1	-0,014	0,185	0,853	Invalid
Work culture → Adaptability	H2	0,447	3,264	0,001	Valid
Adaptability → Performance	H3	0,908	12,68	0,000	Valid
Work culture → Adaptability → Performance	H4	0,406	3,730	0,000	Valid

Discussion

1. The effect of work culture on performance

The finding that work culture does not have a significant direct effect on employee performance in the Bontang City Government is an interesting result and different from most previous studies. Aggarwal (2024), Hung et al. (2022), and Pham et al. (2024) generally found that work culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance in the private sector. However, in the context of this study, a negative (-0.014) and insignificant path coefficient indicates a unique dynamic in public sector organizations that already have a strong and deep-rooted local work culture. A theoretical explanation for these findings can be referred to the organizational culture theory of Robbins & Judge (2024, 561) which states that a strong organizational culture can serve as an informal control mechanism. In the Bontang City Government, the local work culture has been embedded long before the launch of the core values BerAKHLAK in 2021, as reflected in the Circular Letter of the Mayor of Bontang Number 003/566.2/ORG.3 year 2016 concerning the implementation of morning apples with the chants "Bontang City ASN are extraordinary, professional, dignified" and updated with Circular Letter Number 188.65/66/ORG/2022 concerning "Bontang City ASN are professional, great, civilized". The existence of a local work culture that has been internalized in employees' daily lives causes the values of BerAKHLAK to not have a significant additional influence on performance. Cameron & Quinn (2020, 144) in the theory of the Competing Values Framework explain that in mature organizations, work culture often functions as a "hygiene factor" that maintains consistency in performance, not as a driving factor for performance improvement. In other words, when the work culture is already at an adequate level, the addition of new values does not necessarily improve performance linearly. The negative path coefficient value also provides an indication that the implementation of a work culture without clear boundaries has the potential to reduce performance. For example, service-oriented indicators that are over-implemented without regard to standard operating procedures can reduce the efficiency of time and quantity of work results.

2. The effect of work culture on adaptability

The results of the study prove that work culture has a positive and significant effect on the adaptability of employees with a large effect size ($f^2 = 0.250$). These findings are in line with research by Brahm et al. (2024), Park et al. (2020), and Wallin (2024) that concluded that a positive work culture especially one that emphasizes openness, collaboration, and learning encourages employees' adaptive behavior in the face of change. Theoretical explanations based on Robbins & Judge (2024, 565) assert that a culture that emphasizes flexibility, innovation, and openness to change will create a safe psychological climate, making it easier for employees to accept new ideas, adapt behaviors, and learn different ways of working. In the context of the Bontang City Government, work culture values such as collaborative (average 4.60) and harmonious (average 4.57) create a supportive work environment, where employees feel safe to try new approaches and learn from mistakes. In this study, it was found that collaborative indicators had the highest average in work culture variables, while positive responses to feedback had the highest average in adaptability variables. This shows that a culture of collaboration and openness to suggestions and inputs is an important foundation for the development of employees' adaptive capacity. Shojaei et al. (2022) in their research on public organizations assert that organizations that emphasize the value of feedback tend to have more resilient members and are quick to adapt to policy changes. Thus, strengthening work culture indirectly builds the adaptive capacity of employees in responding to organizational dynamics after equalization.

3. The effect adaptability on performance

The finding that adaptability has a positive and very significant effect on performance (coefficient 0.908; p-value 0.000) with a very large effect size ($f^2 = 3.533$) confirms the central position of adaptability as a determinant of performance in the era of organizational change. These results are in line with research by Juna et al. (2024), Meng et al. (2024), and Fernandez et al. (2023) which found that individuals with high adaptability tend to perform better, especially in dynamic work contexts.

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A strong theoretical explanation for this finding can be referred to the Resource-Based View (RBV) theory put forward by Barney (2018) in Cameron & Quinn (2020). RBV states that adaptive ability is a valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable internal resource, thus becoming a source of organizational competitive advantage. In the context of employees' individuals, adaptability allows them to quickly transform knowledge and skills in responding to the demands of new jobs, which ultimately increases work effectiveness and productivity. Further analysis found that the indicator of the ability to learn new skills had the highest outer loading (0.915) in forming the construct of adaptability, although in the descriptive analysis this indicator had the lowest average (3.83). This indicates that structurally, the willingness and speed of learning new skills is the most important pillar in adaptability, but in practice employees still experience difficulties in this aspect. In contrast, positive responses to feedback had the highest average (4.43) but lower outer loading (0.763), indicating that the attitude of receiving input is easier to realize than the actual behavior of learning new competencies. These findings provide important implications that human resource development interventions need to be focused on increasing technical learning capacity and accelerating the mastery of new competencies.

4. The role of adaptability as mediation

This study proves that adaptability as a full mediator in the interconnection between work culture and performance. The impact of work culture on performance is fully channeled through improving employee adaptability. A strong work culture does not directly improve performance, but first strengthens the adaptive capacity of employees, and then that adaptive capacity that encourages performance improvement. These findings are in line with the research of Srimulyani et al. (2025), Katsaros (2025), and Kim et al. (2025) who found the mediating role of adaptability in the relationship between organizational culture and performance. However, this study contributes novelty by revealing that in the context of the Indonesian bureaucracy which already has a strong local work culture, adaptability is the only mechanism for channeling cultural influence on performance. This is in contrast to previous studies that generally found significant direct effects in addition to indirect effects.

A theoretical explanation based on Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 1997) in Srimulyani et al. (2025) provides an in-depth understanding of this mediation mechanism. The theory explains that individuals learn and develop behavior through dynamic interactions between personal factors (cognitive, affective), environment (organizational culture), and the behavior itself. A work culture that supports learning, collaboration, and openness forms employee self-efficacy in the face of change. High self-efficacy then encourages adaptive behaviors such as learning new skills, solving problems in new situations, and managing stress that directly contributes to improved performance. The R-square value for the performance variable of 0.813 indicates that the constructed model has very strong predictive power, where 81.3% a portion of the diversity in performance can be attributed to work culture and adaptability. This emphasizes that in the context of post-equalization, the combination of a conducive work culture and the adaptive capacity of employees is the main determinant of performance achievement. Meanwhile, the R-square value for adaptability of 0.200 indicates that there are still other factors outside of work culture that affect adaptability, such as transformational leadership, organizational support, or individual characteristics like self-efficacy, proactive personality.

Theoretical Implications and Research Novelty

This study enriches the literature on mediation mechanisms that link contextual variables of work culture with individual performance outcomes, by confirming that adaptability plays a role as a full mediator in the context of organizations that already have a strong culture. This research also strengthens the application of the Resource-Based View (RBV) by demonstrating that collective adaptability can be conceptualized as an organizational capability developed and strengthened by a conducive work culture. Furthermore, this research becomes a link between the literature on organizational culture and change management by empirically testing the model in the specific context of bureaucratic reform, namely the equalization of positions from structural to functional. All work culture indicators based on the PANRB Ministerial Circular Letter number 20 year 2021 have been proven to have high validity and reliability, thus providing an empirical basis for the measurement of the work culture construct of civil apparatus in Indonesia. The main novelty of this study lies in the finding that the work culture of AKHLAK does not have a direct effect on performance because there has been a strong local work culture in the Bontang City Government. This finding is different from previous studies that generally found significant direct influences. This indicates that in organizations with mature cultures, the reinforcement of new values does not necessarily improve performance in a linear manner, but rather requires intermediary mechanisms such as adaptive capacity development. Therefore, this research makes an important contribution to understanding the complexity of the relationship between work culture and performance in the context of public organizations in Indonesia.

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CONCLUSION

This study proves that the work culture BerAKHLAK does not have a significant effect directly on employee performance, but through the mediation of employee adaptability. Unique dynamics in public sector organizations that already have a strong local work culture and are rooted first, such as the slogan "ASN who are extraordinary, professional, dignified" which has been internalized through various Mayoral circulars since 2016. Adaptability is proven to be the main determinant of performance with a very large effect size, where the ability to learn new skills is the most dominant indicator in shaping the adaptation construct, although descriptively it is still the lowest aspect felt by employees. Furthermore, the model was able to explain 81.3% of performance variance, confirming that the combination of a conducive work culture and the adaptive capacity of employees is a key predictor of the successful implementation of the equalization policy.

This research makes an important theoretical contribution to the science of human resource management in the context of the public sector. First, this study enriches the literature on mediation mechanisms by proving that adaptability plays a role as a full mediator in the relationship between work culture and performance. Second, this study strengthens the application of Resource-Based View (RBV) and Social Cognitive Theory in the context of Indonesian bureaucracy, by demonstrating that collective adaptability is an organizational capability developed through a conducive work culture. Third, this study validates the instrument for measuring work culture and provides an empirical basis for the measurement of the construction of ASN work culture in Indonesia that can be used for future research purposes. The constraint of this study is the sample size used is relatively limited and includes only one local government, so generalization of the findings to a broader context needs to be done carefully. Second, the cross-sectional research design does not allow researchers to capture the dynamics of changes between variables in a certain time span, even though the process of adaptation and internalization of work culture is longitudinal. Third, the R-square value for the adaptability variable of 20% indicates that there are many other factors outside of work culture that affect adaptability, such as transformational leadership, organizational support, or individual characteristics (self-efficacy, proactive personality), that have not been explored in this study.

This study recommends that human resource development programs not only focus on socializing work culture values, but systematically design interventions to improve employee adaptability. New technical skills-based training programs, intensive coaching and mentoring, 360-degree feedback systems, and collaborative discussion forums between work units need to be implemented in a structured and sustainable manner. In addition, local governments need to establish a periodic evaluation mechanism for the level of employee adaptation after organizational change policies, so that interventions can be targeted and data-based. On a broader scale, these findings can be an input for the Ministry of PANRB and BKN in formulating employee competency development policies that not only emphasize cultural aspects, but also on strengthening adaptive capacity as a prerequisite for improving performance in the midst of changing bureaucratic dynamics.

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